

ADAPTIVE TRAVEL CUP

Akhil Hayash M ^[1], Ashok Kumar A ^[2], Devadarshan I ^[3], Gokul P S^[4]

¹ College of Engineering Trivandrum, Sreekaryam, Trivandrum, Kerala, India. 695016

Abstract:

The primary use of travel cup is to provide the hot water for those who needed especially for the older people whenever they want. If we are at home, we are avail with varieties of options such as from the fire pit, gas stove, induction cooker as well as the electric kettle which is the way more convenient and simpler as well as easy to use. But the normal electric kettle is bulkier in size and not so useful during the journey. During a journey, it is difficult to keep a hot water with us, so the easiest way is to produce the hot water whenever we need. So, we are having a travel cup which has the dimensions nearly to an ordinary cup which could produce the hot water within a short span of time, convenient to use, cheaper, and which can hold the temperature for a certain period of time as well as which could operate using electricity.

being utilized for the purpose of carrying these drinks as they can easily be warmed in a microwave without destroying the container. Consumers, therefore, tend to focus on the advantages of disposable cups and not assume the health hazards that can be caused by styrene cups and the environmental liability in utilizing plastic cups. In addition, the reusable mugs are not able to adequately control the temperature of the drink contained in them over extended periods. The heating and cooling processes can be accomplished by utilizing a variety of methods such as resistive heating and refrigeration cycles respectively. In addition, a micro thermoelectric plate, a Peltier element, functions as a heating and cooling source and operates in small areas.

Keywords: Travel Cup, Adaptive Equipment.

1. Introduction

The advent of travel mugs can be traced back to the 1980s to help people who were travelling preserve the desired to help people who were travelling preserve the desired temperatures of their beverages. Whether one wants their drink to remain cold or hot, a travel mug helps accomplish the task due to thermal insulation properties. However, the mug is not sealed at all times as the drinking opening at the top remains open leading to heat transfer with the surrounding. The temperature of the contained beverage is greatly affected by the temperature of its surroundings and therefore, hot beverages will lose their optimum desirable temperature and that applies for cold drinks as well. Styrene and plastic cups are increasingly

The above figure shows the cup design, the cup is designed so that every age group person could handle it properly. It shows the outer structure of the travel cup. There are two small holes which are shown in the figure by which one is for switch and other is for plug by which the travel cup would get the power for its working. The port is just the USB C port which is just universal now.

The above shown figure is the lid of the travel cup. The lid is made of plastic and had a hole at its center. The lid is made for 2 purposes such as to use as a coaster as well a lid for the travel so as to ensure the safety as well as for aesthetic appearance.

The above figure represents the operating conditions of the travel cup. the figure represents the use of lid as a coaster. There are some grooves which are attached to the lid so that the travel cup will get into it with now issues and also some grooves with more diameter so as to attach to with the top of the cup to as a lid.

The above figure shows the overall view of the travel cup by which anyone could understand the design and shape of the travel cup.

The above figure shows the cross-sectional view of the travel cup. The cross-sectional view give-us how the travel cup is arranged so far. It has some unique layers for its optimized performance. The inner layer or the can is made of high-grade steel and there is layer of poly urethane for better thermal insulation so that the heat thus generated will not get lost over time and also it will be really great for handling the travel cup. The outer layer is made of high-density plastic for better drop protection and high yield.

2. Literature Review

- As the from the conference “Smart Travel Mug for Hot and Cold Beverages”, Hussain F. Alsaif Wentworth Institute of Technology, 2017 we could get a view how the smart travel cups are designed and what are the parameters that needed to be considered on a travel cup.
- As the preceding from the “Volume 1, 2018, Pages 265-339, comprehensive energy system”, Ibrahim Dincer, University of Ontario Institute of Technology, Oshawa, ON, Canada, we are able to find and study how the resistive heating works and its implementations in a practical case.
- “Activated carbon 2006, pages 454-508”, Harry Marsh, FranciscoRodríguez-Reinoso gives the properties of the graphite material so that material selection is easy.
- As from the report “procedures for predicting long-term thermal performance of foam insulations” 1994, by mark bomberg and mavinkal kumaran. We could study about the form type thermal insulator.

3. Research Methodology

For every product that we need to design, we need some data as input. Here in this case, we are having quantitative data over the qualitative data. The data is collected from the various sources such as already established. The proposed design is optimised for 250 ML which is a standard cup size. The difficulties of the travel cup we are having now is obtained from the mass people outside. The technical side is handled with the help of faculty and from the journals mentioned in the literature review.

The above figure will represent the block diagram of the travel cup. We are using sensors such as pressure and temperature sensor so that the operation of the travel cup can be controlled. There will be a controller IC so as to control all these sensors. The entire system is consisting of power supply, safety module, control unit and a heating unit. The power supply will be the AC type. There will be a rectifier in the circuit so as to convert AC into DC. The system will work only if all the criteria are met such as if the cup contains minimum quantity of water and the lid is closed. The heating will get stop if the output from the thermostat reaches required value.

3.1 Heating Unit

Power: Ac Input
 Input: Control Signals from the Control Unit
 Outputs: None

The heating unit has only one mode of operation, such that once water is added and switched on, the coil needed to be heated and thus the water needed to be heated to the temperature of the rate of 100 centigrade. Once it reached 100 centigrade the

heating needed to be stopped so as to protect the cup as well as to eliminate the power wastage.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
1. Able to raise the temperature of 250 ml (250gm) of water from the room temperature (25-30 centigrade) to the 100 centigrade within 80 seconds under standard conditions.	I. Add 250 ml (250gm) of water or till the marked position of the cup II. Plug the instrument with cable provided. III. Place the coaster- lid on the top of the cup IV. Switch on the device by toggling the switch provided on the base of the travel cup V. Wait until the water gets its temperature and stops automatically

3.2 Control Unit

Power: 5V

DC Inputs: Temperature data, User requests, Safety Circuit.

Outputs: Control signals to the heating The Control Unit Will Take 3 Inputs.

The control unit will control the whole operations of the system. the control unit will work on the 5v DC supply. the control unit will work primarily on the basis of 3 inputs. The data from the temperature sensor, the input from the switch which is determined by the user and the input from the safety circuit.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
1. Needed To Switch On While The Switch Is In Closed Position.	I. Check once the temperature of the water is rasing once the device is switched ON
2. Needed To Be Switched Off Once The Required Temperature Is Attained.	II. Check whether the device the turning off once the temperature (say 100 centigrade) is attained
3. Only Needed To Be Switched Once The Lid Is Topped On The Top Of The Travel Cup	III. Check whether the device is turning ON without closing the lid-coaster

3.3 Sensors

Input: 5v from the power supply

Outputs: water temperature reading for the control unit, pressure reading from the pressure sensor to the control unit, logic 0,1 from the safety network. this module measures the temperature of water (or any other liquid inside the container), measures the pressure developed as well as logic state from the safety network provided and sends the measurement to the control unit. we are planning to use a contactless sensor for this module.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
1. Should not be started until the Logic state is 1	I. Check whether there is a voltage once the lid is closed
2. There should be a resistance change once the temperature is changed	II. Check whether the resistance is changing once shown to flame
3. There should be some reading from the pressure sensor	III. Check whether there is a out once loaded

3.4 Power Supply

Outputs (power): 5v for the control unit, thermostat for water, user interface, pressure sensor and temperature sensor in safety module, ac supply from the source to the heating element.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
1. The voltage to the electronic part should be 5V	I. The out from the SMPS is of the order of 5V DC
2. The supply to the heating element is the main supply itself.	II. The supply to the heating coil is in the order of high voltage AC.

The above figure will show us the flowchart of the controller circuit that we use in this travel cup. The conditions are given and once all the conditions are met and button is pressed, the travel cup will heat the water to the required temperature and once required temperature (say 100 degree centigrade) is met, the heating will get stop.